

THE METHODOLOGY OF SPEECH LITERACY DEVELOPMENT THROUGH THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article, it is necessary to form the form of literary and artistic speech through practical, regular and consistent teaching of the native language based on examples and special exercises. It is reported that the main task of primary class mother tongue classes is to prepare students for educational activities, to form a person who can communicate with others, who can convey his opinion to others in an understandable way.*

Keywords: *speech, written speech, speech culture, elementary school, students, methodology, native language classes, grammar, logic.*

INTRODUCTION

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained state independence, the fundamental improvement of the structure and content of education of secondary educational institutions, in particular, primary education students, is becoming a priority. For this purpose, the National Personnel Training Program was approved in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education, and it is "a science based on national and universal moral values, work skills, creative thinking, a conscious attitude to the world and choosing a profession. aimed at ensuring the acquisition of systematic knowledge on the basics, strengthening the need to acquire knowledge, basic educational, scientific and general cultural knowledge, and the formation of spiritual and moral qualities.

The science of the mother tongue helps to expand the thinking activity of young children, to be able to think freely, to listen to the opinions of others, to be able to express their thoughts fluently orally and in writing, to be able to communicate freely with members of society, and serves to develop skills. In this place, mother tongue education is considered not as an educational subject, but as an educational process that organizes the entire educational system. The type of activity of a speaker is the use of thinking based on language tools (words, phrases, sentences). Speech performs the function of communication and message, expressing one's thoughts with emotions and influencing others. A well-developed speech serves as one of the important tools of human activity in society. For the student, speech is a tool for successful education at school.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In turn, connected speech serves as a means of enriching the vocabulary of the story and essay. Developing written speech is a more complex process than oral speech. Because it requires students to construct correct sentences in terms of grammar and content, to use each word correctly in its place, to express ideas concisely, coherently, expressively, and in terms of style, simply and fluently. , requires making conclusions based on the stated opinions. The complex nature of this speech is also related to spelling, punctuation, and style. Writing the word correctly, using

punctuation marks appropriately, expressing the idea in accordance with the requirements of the style requires a great responsibility from the student. Therefore, this type of speech is rather slow and complex. Another characteristic of written speech is that it can be checked, corrected, and improved. In this respect, it has more favorable opportunities than oral speech. The student works on mistakes and shortcomings in written speech, eliminates them, and tries to avoid these mistakes and shortcomings in his next work. The teacher should not forget that students often pay a lot of attention to spelling and punctuation in written works and do not work enough on the content of the text. Texts are often dominated by ideas that are not related to the topic, and the main idea is neglected. That's why in native language lessons, students' attention is not only on spelling and punctuation, but also on the fact that the expressed idea has reasonable arguments, the correct placement of the material, and the correct expression of the idea in accordance with the speech conditions. should be focused. In mother tongue classes, it is necessary to create such a situation that the student is satisfied with the text he created. This inspires him to improve his speech. If the students think creatively independently and are able to express the product of their thoughts correctly and fluently in oral and written forms in accordance with the speech conditions, then the native language classes will be conducted effectively.

According to the scientific data given in pedagogical books, 2-year-old children from 30 to 100, 4-year-old children from 1000 to 4000, 7-year-old children from 3000 to 7000, 10-11-year-old children from 8000 to 15000, 14-15-year-olds from 11000 to 18000 they must know the word. But, unfortunately, when it is necessary to express the thought in the form of oral and written form in the training of the native language, the poverty of words in the students is immediately noticeable. Repeated use of words in speech, not being able to replace a given word with its meaning, synonym and opposite meaning, difficulties encountered in compiling a dictionary of words related to a certain field are undoubtedly indicates that the students' vocabulary is not enough. Another factor that complicates the development of students' speech in mother-tongue classes is that students speak Tajik, Turkmen, Kyrgyz or another (dialect) at home, on the street, or outside of class, and speak Uzbek at school. it is winter. Ethnographic data show that a large number of Tajiks, Turkmens, Kyrgyz, and Kazakhs live in the territory of our republic. Most of them spoke Tajik, Kyrgyz, etc. at home and studied in Uzbek at school. This situation, without a doubt, limits the possibility for students to freely express their thoughts using the rich possibilities of the language. In addition to the above-mentioned negative factors, there is a lack of content and content of the work carried out in our mother tongue outside of the classroom and school, not always following a uniform speech mode, parents' insufficient work on the child's speech, such as oral and written problems of students. negatively affects the development of speech. So, the development of the student's speech is a complex process, and the factors hindering it do not depend only on the content of education or the teacher. The process of teaching to express thoughts correctly and fluently orally and in writing will be easy only if all opportunities are used to the fullest. It opens a wide path to the development of the student's speech. As we know, students get bored of sameness. Therefore, it is necessary to use various methods and games to develop their speech. Below I will give some of them as an example. "Story" The teacher writes a few words on the blackboard. For example: Elegance, rain, watch and literature. Pupils independently compose a story with the participation of these words.

In particular, the formation of speech culture in primary classes is an urgent issue today. Working on the correctness of speech Improving the speech culture of elementary school students

is considered one of the main areas of the teacher's educational and methodological activity. The issue of formation of speech culture occupied a central place in the works of Eastern thinkers of the distant past. Farobi says the following about speaking correctly, making logical conclusions, and being a meaningful and beautiful speaker: - How to teach and receive, how to express, explain, how to ask and when we come to answer, I confirm that the first science about this is the science of language, which gives names to bodies, i.e., substance (independent, self-existent) and accidentia (accidental manifestation).

The second science is grammar: it teaches how to arrange the names given to objects, and how to compose words of wisdom and speech expressing the arrangement of substance and accident and the resulting result.

The third science is logic: it teaches how to arrange propositions according to logical figures in order to produce certain conclusions, with the help of which we can know what we do not know and judge what is true and what is false. The term speech is derived from the Arabic word, speaking, speech; means the ability to speak. Use of language in the processes of expression and exchange of ideas; the process of using language tools by the speaker and the result of this process.

It is known that many people have been interested in the place and role of speech and thinking in human life since ancient times. Thinkers such as Farobi, Zamakhshari, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Kaikovus, Alisher Navoi noted speech as one of the signs of spiritual perfection in their works. For example, Farobi says about the power of speech: —...the power of speech (speech) is such a power that a person acquires knowledge and skills with the help of it, with the help of which he can distinguish between ugly and beautiful actions in his behavior, and what needs to be done -does things that are not good, and at the same time understands what is harmful and what is useful, what is tasty and what is bitter.

RESULTS

M. Koshgari's "Devon-u Lughatit" Turkish work contains the proverb "Adab boshi - language". This shows that our great ancestors emphasized the importance of language in the formation and development of human spirituality.

Yusuf Khos Hajib says that education and knowledge are manifested in a person through language and words, and calls for fluency in speech: "language is the interpreter and translator of education and knowledge."

Enlightenment, goodness and goodness come to a person because of the language, it is necessary to know this well. A person finds fame and reputation through language.

Never talk too much. In very few words. Write down the word cloud in one word, that is, divide it into fewer words to give more meaning.

Kaikovus recognizes the culture of speaking in his "Nightmare" as follows: "... when you speak in front of the people, let your words be beautiful, let the people accept these words."

Let the people know that you have reached a high level with your words, because they know a person's career through words, everyone's condition is hidden under his words. The issue of developing the speech of elementary school students is solved in current methodological literature based on different approaches to knowledge about language, vocabulary and speech culture.

Based on the linguistic concepts included in the elementary school mother tongue program, exercises can be divided into phonetic, lexical, word formation, morphemic (word composition), graphic, orthographic, orthoepic, grammatical exercises.

The analysis carried out on the basis of these exercises is comprehensive in terms of helping students to master theoretical concepts, enriching their vocabulary, developing their connected speech, and provides students with a comprehensive mastery of the language. It should be noted that the analysis of the language of the exercise texts in the mother tongue textbooks of the primary class, the questions developed on them, showed that they do not have the opportunity to gradually develop the students' speech. Although all the exercise texts in native language textbooks help to strengthen and expand theoretical knowledge, they cannot be the basis for students' vocabulary enrichment, speech development, and practical acquisition of the language.

The fact that the exercises have not achieved perfection as a system, they are composed of thematic sentences intended to provide theoretical information, undoubtedly, the exercises have little positive effect on the acquisition of connected speech. A poor text in the form of a simple colloquial speech cannot be a source for enriching the student's speech. Students' mastery of the Uzbek literary language depends on the artistry of the exercise texts and the richness of language components.

Conducting lessons by means of didactic games also helps children to engage in mental activity faster and to develop adaptation. Didactic games can be used to increase the students' interest in the lesson at the beginning of a new lesson or during the reinforcement of the previous lesson.

Here are some examples of games that can be used in elementary school mother tongue classes:

Chain game. The teacher says a word that has a synonym in the language, and the students find a word that has a meaning in the order of the table and say it.

CONCLUSION

When there is no meaning left, the next student himself helps to continue the game by saying a word that has a meaning in the language. A number of desk students can form several groups of words with the same meaning. The game continues in sequence. For example, if 10 students are sitting in a row, they can form groups of three or four rhyming words. After completing exercise 304 in the 4th grade, this game can be organized.

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